

Analysing data from interviews in qualitative research

OER

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Collecting data is a crucial step in research. Researchers gather information related to the topic of study through various methods, such as interviewing. Based on the research question and the problem we are studying, we can develop the research design and select the qualitative data collection methods we will use (Billups, 2021). Once we have designed our study, we move on to the empirical phase, where we collect and then analyse the data.

According to Robert S. Weiss (1994), researchers can only give full attention to analyzing and writing the report after the interviews have ended. The goal of the analysis “is to reach some inferences, lessons, or conclusions by condensing large amounts of data into relatively smaller, more manageable bits of understandable information” (Sheppard, 2020, p. 259).

Before conducting interviews, researchers need to make decisions about sampling, design, key concepts, and participant consent. Several handbooks on interviewing in social science research offer detailed insights into these stages. It's important to note that this Open Educational Resource (OER) does not delve into participant selection or interview conduct. Our primary goal is to provide students and researchers with a valuable tool for comprehending the analysis of data gathered through interviews, with a specific focus on developing thematic analysis.

1. Interviews as a data collection method

Interviews are a data collection method commonly used in qualitative research and included in many research methodology handbooks (Cairns-Lee et al., 2022). In-depth interviews are structured encounters between a researcher and a participant aimed at obtaining information (Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005). Interviews involve a structured process of data collection through conversations between a researcher, who asks questions, and a

participant, who answers them (Knott et al., 2022). Typically, the participant takes a passive role, responding to a set of questions and seeking clarification from the interviewer as needed (Gubrium & Holstein, 2001). In addition, interviews should be viewed as a tool for collecting data in accordance with the research question. They can be combined with other qualitative methods, such as ethnography, or with quantitative methods, such as surveys (Knott et al., 2022, p. 1).

Interviewing remains one of the most common qualitative methods of data collection, which is evidenced in some facts: around a third (78) of the research articles published in *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science* between 2011 and 2021 have used interviewing (Cairns-Lee et al., 2022, p. 164). One reason behind this could be that interviews allow the researchers to access the observations of others, including places they have not visited or experiences they have not had.

We can learn also, through interviewing, about people's interior experiences. We can learn what people perceived and how they interpreted their perceptions. We can learn how events affected their thoughts and feelings. We can learn the meanings to them of their relationships, their families, their work, and their selves. We can learn about all the experiences, from joy through grief, that together constitute the human condition. (Weiss, 1994, p. 1)

In-depth interviews can be categorized based on their structural level. Highly structured interviews are akin to surveys, utilizing a detailed guide. Semi-structured interviews employ a topic guide, while entirely unstructured interviews lack any guiding framework. Structured or standardized interviews are commonly employed in quantitative or survey research, involving the presentation of the same set of specific questions (referred to as 'closed') to each participant. This method aims to generalize beyond the immediate sample and test hypotheses (Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005). In contrast, unstructured interviews allow research participants to share their stories extensively, using their own words, with minimal direction or intervention from researchers. Lastly, semi-structured interviews involve

planned yet flexible questions, incorporating a mix of open and closed responses (Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005).

2. The interviews are complete, so what comes next?

Upon concluding all the interviews, our focus shifts to the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data. Often, we are faced with the challenging task of handling hundreds of minutes of recordings, and this raw information requires comprehensive processing and analysis. For this phase, Brinkmann (2013) underscores the common frustration experienced by many experienced qualitative interviewers who, despite enjoying the interview process, find themselves grappling with an extensive amount of data—potentially hundreds or even thousands of pages of transcripts—without a clear strategy for transforming this material into a robust, relevant, and thought-provoking analysis (Brinkmann, 2013, p. 3).

Throughout the interview process, researchers must follow a series of diverse steps, including selecting questions, participant sampling coding, and results interpretation. Maintaining focus on the research question is crucial across all phases. According to Huberman and Miles (1994), preprocessing is essential since initial data is often not readily available for analysis, necessitating corrections, edits, and the transcription of raw notes and tape recordings.

Preparing the data involves making critical decisions. First and foremost is defining the corpus of analysis (Knott et al., 2022). The text to be analysed may include not only interview transcriptions but also notes taken by the researcher or observational comments. This leads to the second decision: how will the transcription process be carried out, given that we need to analyse written text? Researchers face challenges such as mishearings, overinterpretations, and questions related to punctuation. One decision may involve incorporating the participant's words with the researcher's comments or descriptions in square brackets within the transcription.

According to Knott et al. (2022), the process of transcription is one of transformation. The verbal data are transformed into a written transcript through a series of decisions that the researchers make. For instance, researchers need to consider that choosing a specific punctuation style for a sentence could impact the final analysis, and there's a possibility of mishearing what has been said (Knott et al., 2022).

Decisions about including comments and notes should align with the research question and objectives. These decisions can also be influenced by the paradigm guiding the research. Knott et al. clarify that, from a post-positivist standpoint, researchers might focus on the manifest content of the interview (what is said, not how it's said). However, from a constructivist perspective, researchers may opt to capture more aspects of speech, including pauses, repetitions, and false starts (Knott et al., 2022).

Moreover, transcribing all the records can be time-consuming. Nevertheless, for some researchers transcribing manually can be useful, acknowledging that it fosters a deeper understanding and immersion in the data, facilitating efficient coding and thematic analysis (Khan & MacEachen, 2022).

Questions for researchers	Considerations
Are we going to use software to help us?	Currently, there are numerous AI-powered options available for transcribing recordings. It is important to consider the limitations, ethical implications, and benefits of using such technologies. It is worth noting that AI may misinterpret the context and make errors.
Do we have to include other expressions that are not necessary words?	It is up to the researchers to include physical expressions of the participants such as a long breath or tearing. That could be part of the data analysis and should follow the technique that is going to be used to analyse data.
How many times do we have to listen to the recordings and read the transcripts?	As many times as necessary. But do not forget to prioritise the tasks and be aware of the limitations in terms of time and resources. To start the thematic analysis, we recommend listening to the whole recording and reading the whole transcript at least once.

With all of these, there are many paths to walk when analysing qualitative data. However, we can emphasise certain common practices that can assist researchers in this process. Milles and Huberman (1994) proposed a sequence to do it:

1. Affixing codes to a set of field notes drawn from observations or interviews.
2. Noting reflections or other remarks in the margins.
3. Sorting and sifting through these materials to identify similar phrases, relationships between variables, patterns, themes, distinct differences between subgroups, and common sequences.
4. Isolating these patterns and processes, commonalities and differences, and taking them out to the field in the next wave of data collection.
5. Gradually elaborating a small set of generalizations that cover the consistencies discerned in the data.
6. Confronting those generalizations with a formalized body of knowledge in the form of constructs or theories.

3. Methods to analyse interview data

After getting done with the process of organising and preparing the data, we need to analyse it. The key aspects of the data are captured through coding, which reduces the complexity by providing a smaller number of more abstract terms (Leavy, 2014). This information is the subject of our analysis. Depending on our perspective and the theoretical framework employed, researchers should establish categories, both broad and more specific, to classify the data.

There are various methods researchers can employ for qualitative analysis including narrative analysis, qualitative content analysis, grounded theory method, discourse analysis, thematic analysis, sentiment analysis, interpretative phenomenological analysis, conversation analysis, and more. For detailed information on each method, referring to literature on qualitative data analysis is advisable. The chosen perspective(s) will guide our interpretation of the gathered information. Nevertheless, it is possible to combine multiple

methods to analyze data, depending on the object of analysis. For instance, researchers might conduct a thematic analysis to organize collected data and subsequently apply discourse analysis (Knott et al., 2022).

One of the most common methods to analyse data is thematic analysis, which is focused on the analysis of the topics covered in the interview. Following, we will develop more deeply the main ideas of this method and describe in which situations it is common to use it. We decided to centre our attention on thematic analysis exclusively because it is commonly used in social studies and because for some academics it does not require detailed theoretical or technical background such as in content analysis or grounded theory.

4. What is thematic analysis and how to do it

Thematic analysis is -for some scholars such as Victoria Clarke and Virginia Braun- the foundational method for qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This method is useful in research because identifying thematic meanings is one of the shared generic skills across qualitative analysis (Holloway and Todres, 2003, as cited in Braun and Clarke, 2006). For this reason, some scholars would not classify it as a method but as a tool. The basis of this method is identifying themes or patterns of meaning in the whole database, and the possibility of describing and interpreting them (Braun et al., 2016).

How can we know if this method is suitable for our research? According to Braun, Clarke and Weate (2016), thematic analysis is suitable for a broad spectrum of research questions, particularly those involving people's experiences, patterns in practices and behaviours, perspectives on specific issues, or the representation of issues, for example, in the media.

The same authors highlight two "strands" of the thematic analysis: 1. the "small q" qualitative research, linked to a realist ontological framework; and 2. the "big Q", which is not linked to a specific theoretical tradition and can be applied across a spectrum of qualitative paradigms (Kidder & Fine, 1987 as cited in (Braun et al., 2016). This may sound a bit confusing. In simpler terms, in the 'small q' versions of thematic analysis, coding frames and

codes can be created to find meanings within the dataset. On the other hand, the 'big Q' allows researchers to identify patterns more robustly without attaching a specific ontological or epistemological anchor (Braun et al., 2016). However, it is always important for researchers to make evident from what perspective they are analysing data, understanding that “any theoretical framework carries with it a number of assumptions about the nature of the data, what they represent in terms of the „the world“, „reality“, and so forth. A good thematic analysis will make this transparent” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 9).

According to Braun, Clarke and Weate, researchers need to make some active choices to develop a good analysis. Firstly, the data level: are we going to engage with the obvious and explicit meanings expressed by the research participants (we can call it *semantic*) or the meanings and frameworks behind or underpinned in what the participants said, which let us analyse and code from the implicit ideas and concepts (we call it *latent*). The latter can be harder to identify (Braun et al., 2016). To exemplify this, imagine that we are researching teenage pregnancy, and one of the participants talks about the lack of literacy regarding contraception methods in schools, from a semantic perspective we can develop a theme about the lack of literacy; but if we notice that that lack of literacy is connected with the challenges for women accessing education, then we should develop another theme about inequalities in the access to sexual education.

Secondly, we need to make a choice related to the approach that we are going to use for data coding and theme development. From a deductive approach, the analysis is driven by theoretical concepts beyond the data and tends to offer a detailed analysis of a specific aspect of the data, rather than providing a comprehensive description of the data as a whole. In contrast, the inductive approach is where data and content guide and drive the analysis (Braun et al., 2016). An inductive approach involves identifying themes that are strongly linked to the data itself, in this process of data-coding we should not try to fit it into a pre-existing coding frame or behind researchers' analytical preconceptions (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Thirdly, we need to select a framework to guide us. This can be based on conceptual, epistemological, or ontological frameworks such as realism or post-positivism, or from a critical/constructionist perspective. Thematic analysis can be conducted within both realist/essentialist and constructionist paradigms. However, the outcomes and focus will differ between the two approaches (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

We can mix those decisions and that way we can develop a thematic analysis, however usually some options tend to get along with others more naturally. For example, the critical/constructionist with a deductive approach and focuses on a latent level. In the end, due to the broad nature of thematic analysis, researchers have the flexibility to employ a mix of approaches. This could involve using both inductive and deductive methods or addressing the analysis at both the latent and semantic levels, depending on the specific research questions.

4.1. Steps to do a thematic analysis

For this OER we utilize the concept and methodology of thematic analysis developed by Braun, Clarke, and Weate in their texts from 2006, 2013, 2016, and 2017. They have compiled diverse theories and practices related to thematic analysis in the social sciences from various authors. The authors present a six-phase model for conducting thematic analysis; however, these steps serve as a guide. In this regard, researchers must exercise critical judgment in their application and should always bear in mind that, as researchers, we need to make active choices, be reflective, and engage in conscious deliberations.

Conducting effective thematic analysis involves a recursive and reflective process, moving forward and sometimes backwards through stages such as data familiarization, coding, theme development, revision, naming, and the final write-up. It is important to note that the analysis is not inherent in the data, waiting to be discovered, and themes do not simply 'emerge' (Braun et al., 2016, p. 7).

a. Phase 1: familiarising yourself with your data

For those who run the interviews, it is likely that they already have some knowledge about the content before diving into the coding phase. As a best practice, we recommend

reading through the entire dataset at least once before commencing coding. This initial phase serves as an opportunity to take notes and generate preliminary coding ideas. Furthermore, in this stage, we will transcribe the interviews. As mentioned earlier, in this process, critical decisions must be made regarding what content will be included in our dataset.

b. Phase 2: generating initial codes

This is the moment when we should create a list of ideas about what is in the data set. The first codes that we propose should be identified in the data (semantic if the themes are data-driven or latent content if theory-driven) and refer to “the most basic segment, or element, of the raw data or information that can be assessed in a meaningful way regarding the phenomenon” (Boyatzis, 1998 as cited in (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 18).

As previously mentioned, coding can be undertaken manually or with the aid of software. Regardless, the core concept involves systematically reading and coding the entire dataset, meticulously attending to all items to identify intriguing aspects that may later evolve into patterns. It is crucial to organize the extracted content under the assigned codes. Here are some guidelines for researchers: a text extract can be coded more than once if it fits into different codes; similarly, a fragment may remain uncoded; during the selection of fragments, context or surroundings can be included; and strive to code as many themes as possible, as subsequent filtering can be applied.

c. Phase 3: searching for themes

After finishing all the initial coding and collation, we will have a list of different codes. We need to find broader themes within the codes, and how some fit with others. More simply, as we begin to analyse our codes, we need to consider how they may combine to form an overarching theme (Braun & Clarke, 2006). To do this, we might need to use a table, mind map or another type of graphic. Here it is important to notice that we can have overarching themes, themes and sub-themes, also we may end up with some codes without any theme, in that case, we can save them and group them in a miscellaneous tag.

d. Phase 4: reviewing themes

During this phase, we must confirm, modify, or eliminate candidate themes. It is necessary to review the data for each candidate and determine if the entire 'theme category' is adequately supported, requires additional data, or should be combined with another category. Alternatively, it may be necessary to divide some themes into two separate categories.

To review the themes, we can do it in two levels. In the first level, we revise the codes and the extracts categorized in each one, reading all the collated extracts for each theme, and considering whether they form a coherent pattern. If they do not, we need to check if they fit into another theme or if the theme needs editing. Then, at the second level, we do the same but with the entire dataset. Here, we should consider if the individual themes work in relation to the whole dataset and whether our candidate thematic map reflects the meanings evident in it. If something is not working, we need to go back and revise the codes, the extracts, the themes, and the map, either to modify some themes or create new ones.

e. Phase 5: defining and naming themes

Now that we have an idea of our different themes and how the dialogue to others, we can choose which themes are going to be included in our analysis. To do that, we need to define and refine the themes that we are using, choosing the scope and the content of each theme. What is this theme about and why is this theme interesting for our research? We need to identify the story in each theme and how it interacts with the other themes.

In every phase there are possibilities to change and edit the codes and the themes, always taking into account the research questions and the discussions we want to develop. Here is a huge remark for students and young researchers: “as coding data and generating themes could go on ad infinitum, it is important not to get over-enthusiastic with endless re-coding” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 21).

f. Phase 6: producing the report

After completing the entire process of coding and crafting themes and subthemes, it's time to embark on the final analysis. The written analysis should not only delineate the relations within each theme, including their interactions with others, but also incorporate

extracts from the transcriptions to substantiate each theme. The goal is to convince our readers of the validity and justification of our analysis. To achieve this, we must employ storytelling resources to effectively convey the ideas and provide examples that illustrate our points. Building compelling arguments beyond the data and our chosen approach is crucial. We have the freedom to transition from the descriptive to the interpretative level, drawing on theories and existing literature. Throughout this phase, the key is to continually pose questions and leverage the data to provide insightful answers. Some examples of those questions can be: “What does this theme mean? What are the assumptions underpinning it? What are the implications? [...] Why do people talk about this thing in this particular way?” and “What is the overall story the different themes reveal about the topic?” (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p. 24)

4.2. Hints to avoid common mistakes

Since thematic analysis is sometimes not considered a method (just a tool), we need to avoid some common risks in using it for qualitative research.

- Interview questions should not be used as themes in thematic analysis. The crucial aspect of the analysis is making sense of the data and identifying patterns or relationships within the dataset.
- Having too many themes and sub-themes can be overwhelming and challenging to work with. Therefore, it is essential to define and refine themes carefully. The definition and extracts should be coherent and consistent.
- In qualitative research, there is always a risk of misinterpreting or overinterpreting data. Anecdotes shared by participants during interviews also pose a risk of misrepresentation. To mitigate these risks, researchers must rely on their character, wisdom, and reasoning.
- The final analysis should be supported by the data. If there is a mismatch between these two our research would be weak and invalid. But at the same time in qualitative research in social sciences can be really rare to find 100% patterns to justify what are we interpreting.

- Thematic analysis should not be superficial. The theoretical framework plays a fundamental role in the interpretation phase of the data. It is important to be aware of the assumptions and how the data relates to them in order to conduct a solid analysis. Furthermore, developing a framework that includes all desired analyses, moves logically between areas, and leads to a general conclusion can be challenging (Weiss, 1994).
- Finally, researchers must be explicit about what they are doing and the limitations of their data collection methods. Theory and method should be applied rigorously.

5. Conclusions

Thematic analysis should be supported by the data to avoid superficiality. The theoretical framework plays a fundamental role in interpreting the data. It is important to keep the research questions in mind from start to finish during the analysis phase. This OER aims to be a useful tool, hence following the steps mentioned before will help researchers maintain focus on the main goal. Each step should be fulfilled rigorously, for instance, becoming familiar with the corpus is essential for the whole analysis.

Doing thematic analysis well includes a back-and-forth process where you go through steps like getting familiar with the data, coding, and defining and redefining themes. The analysis is not already in the data, waiting for us to find it, and themes don't just pop up on their own. Without theory and researchers' criteria, the data is just a group of words.

Conducting thematic analysis demands a rigorous application of theory and methodology, as well as analytical skills, pattern recognition, and reflexivity. Researchers' analytical skills and their ability to identify complex relationships within the data are crucial to successful qualitative research. Indeed, the analysis is strengthened by the clear identification and justification of themes and the connections found within the data and the theory.

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